

MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHANGES OF RAT ADRENAL GLANDS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF AN ENERGY DRINK IN AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The adrenal glands are the main component of the hypothalamic-pituitary system, and the functional state of this organ reflects the adequacy of the adaptive system's response.

Introduction: The adrenal glands are the main component of the hypothalamic-pituitary system, and the functional state of this organ reflects the adequacy of the adaptive system's response.

The literature contains almost no data on the morphological state of the adrenal glands during non-lethal intoxication with energy drinks (ED), which, depending on the dose and duration of exposure, undoubtedly modifies adrenal structure and function. In addition, most morphological studies of the adrenal glands describe either male subjects or combined male and female groups; therefore, sex-related differences in adrenal morphological changes under environmental factors remain insufficiently explored.

Considering the above, the study of the morphofunctional state of the adrenal glands under the influence of energy drinks is highly relevant. The understanding of tissue mechanisms underlying systemic adaptive responses to extreme stimuli remains poorly investigated.

Aim of the study: To investigate the morphological features of adrenal gland changes under the influence of energy drinks.

Materials and Methods: Experimental studies were conducted at the Research Laboratory of the Tashkent Medical Academy on 60 outbred rats. The animals were kept under standard vivarium conditions with a normal maintenance regime. One day before the experiment, the animals were deprived of food while maintaining free access to water. All laboratory animals were carefully examined, weighed, and their age and motor activity were recorded. Before the experiment, all animals were healthy and active.

According to the study design, the animals were divided into two comparable groups:

- **Group 1 (n=40):** outbred rats receiving energy drink enterally.
- **Group 2 (control, n=20):** intact male rats of similar body weight.

The experiments started at 09:00 a.m. The energy drink was administered intragastrically using a gastric tube (modified subclavian catheter) at doses of 2 and 4 ml per 1 kg of body weight. The observation period after administration was 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 hours, after which the animals were sacrificed.

Statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using Student's t-test to assess differences between mean values.

Results and Discussion: Histological examination of the adrenal glands showed that during adaptation to prolonged psychoemotional and physical stress, significant structural changes occur in the adrenal cortex, its microcirculatory bed, and the reticular zone.

In the experimental groups, the reticular zone of the cortex was markedly expanded, and its cells became polygonal and larger compared to the control group. The ratio of the glomerular, fascicular, and reticular zones in the cortex was 1:2:1.

In the glomerular zone, cells were relatively large with small nuclei and abundant pale cytoplasm, indicating significant lipid accumulation and a relatively low level of functional stress.

Conclusion: It was established that prolonged exposure to energy drinks activates the function of the adrenal cortex in experimental animals. The concentration of cortisol in the blood of rats increases by 3.6–4.0 times.

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